

1 **VOLCANIC ATMOSPHERES IMPACT ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF**
2 ***TECTONA GRANDIS* AND *CUPRESSUS LUSITANICA* IN EARLY STAGES OF**
3 **OUTDOOR EXPOSURE**

4
5 **Abstract**

6 This research aimed to evaluate the impact of the volcanic atmosphere on the mechanical
7 properties, modulus of elasticity (MOE), and rupture (MOR), of *Cupressus lusitanica* and *Tectona*
8 *grandis* using structural size specimens in early stages of exposure with time series (3, 6, 9, 12,
9 18, 24, and 30 months. Despite the inter-sites' acid variables (SO₂, pH, SO₄²⁻), no significant
10 differences in MOE-MOR were found. A climate-based model was successfully established to
11 estimate structural-size specimen's MOE in the early degradation stages. The main mechanical
12 properties give a theoretical and practical framework to estimate the material performance of
13 touristic natural facilities.

14 **Keywords:** Wood degradation, Modulus of elasticity MOE, Sulphur dioxide SO₂ Volcanic acid
15 atmospheres, Outdoor exposure.

16
17 **Introduction**

18 Wood has been used as a building material to create diverse structures, houses, bridges, and
19 emblematic buildings. However, when exposed outdoors the natural degradation poses a challenge
20 to maintenance and structural deterioration processes. Numerous investigations have focused on
21 evaluating wood degradation, and service life since this is a key knowledge to promote the use of
22 this sustainable material [1]–[3]. Despite numerous laboratory investigations, the complexity of
23 wood degradation outdoors is influenced by unpredictable weather conditions and their interaction
24 and remains challenging to replicate in the laboratory [4]. Consequently, there is a crucial necessity
25 for field studies, considering climatic variables contributing to wood degradation [5]–[8]. From
26 them, the effect of solar radiation and humidity has been analysed widely, as principal promoters
27 of wood degradation [6]. It is important to remark that moisture reduces mechanical properties due
28 to fibre interactions. The degradation of wood under the action of humidity occurs since wood is
29 a porous material, composed of numerous tubular cells, (cell wall and cell cavity) [4]. Due to the
30 periodic changes in temperature and humidity throughout the year, the cell wall is repeatedly
31 contracted and expanded. The moisture gradients due to constrained shrinkage and swelling may

1 cause cracks [10]–[13]. The effect of long-term humidity changes is especially prominent in humid
2 and hot areas. Where the atmospheric water content is very high. Constant changes in
3 environmental humidity reduce the long-term strength of wood under load, increase creep effects,
4 and lead to excessive deformation, or early damage. It may also affect the bearing capacity and
5 stability of the overall structure [10]. Further, ultraviolet (UV) radiation plays a main role in the
6 depolymerization of wood microstructures affecting lignin and leading chemical reactions [9],
7 [10]. For tropical wood-degradation, rapid changes have been determined within a short period (10
8 months), and important variations in density, colour, and dynamic modulus of elasticity in 5
9 Indonesian woods were reported by Karlinasari, et al. The tropical studied species were
10 *Paraserianthes falcataria*, *Shorea* spp, *Swietenia* spp, *Tectona grandis*), and *Intsia* spp. [11].
11 Similarly, Almeida et al, reported that the mechanical properties of Brazilian woods (*Pinus* sp,
12 (softwood), *Anacardium giganteum*, *Erismia uncinatum*, *Bagassa guianensis*, and *Peltogyne*
13 *lecointei* (hardwoods)) were also affected when subjected to artificial and natural weathering for
14 one year. In this work, the modulus of elasticity (MOE) obtained from static bending tests
15 decreased by MOE_T 13.55% and MOE_C12.96% (tension and compression respectively) [8].
16 However, this mechanical properties reduction was not observed by Van Blokland et al. [12] for
17 Norway spruce (*Picea abies*) weathered for 30 months in Sweden. When evaluating static bending
18 and dynamic stiffness no significant weathering influence was determined despite the cracking
19 process. Additionally, valuable work has been developed on predicting the mechanical properties
20 of weathered wood using different modelling and machine learning techniques, considering colour
21 changes, surface checks, bending properties and wave propagation determined non-destructive
22 testing [13]–[15] In the literature review, wood degradation in volcanic environments has not been
23 reported. In these contexts, the material is influenced by atmospheric chemical factors (acid
24 gases/rain, ash, humidity, and endemic agents). Volcanic emissions contain water vapour (H₂O),
25 carbon dioxide (CO₂), hydrogen sulphide (H₂S), hydrogen chloride (HCl) [16]–[18], and mainly
26 sulphur dioxide (SO₂). Depending on volcanic activity, the presence of these contaminants varies
27 constantly in their concentration [19]. Acid rain is influenced by chemical reactions produced by
28 SO₂. This gas is soluble in the aqueous phase and precipitates when it rains. At typical pH values
29 of cloud water (5.6), the bisulphite ion (HSO_3^-) is dominant formed by the reaction (1)

1 Various mechanisms explain the oxidation of HSO_3^- to sulphuric acid in the aqueous phase, using
2 oxidants absorbed by water from the gas phase participating in the reactions:

3 At low pH, reaction (2) is inhibited, oxidation by H_2O_2 is the dominant reaction (3), and contrary,
4 oxidation by O_3 is more important at high pH [20]. Considering this condition, the sulphuric acid
5 influence in wood needs to be reviewed. In the literature, it has been reported that wood is resistant
6 to dilute aqueous acid solutions at room temperature [21]. It has been established that the intensity
7 of weathering and chemical degradation of wood depends on multiple factors. The acid
8 concentration, its interaction with humidity, temperature, the exposure time, the permeability of
9 the species, the sample thickness and the proportion of the sample exposed ends. Depending on
10 them, acids have the potential to affect wood polymers [22]. Williams reported that at low pH
11 levels, the rate of weathering and fibre breakdown process may increase [23]. The combination of
12 UV light and acid rain may accelerate changes, and induce changes in the wood surface by oxidized
13 products. In other studies, it was reported that the sulfuric acid contributed to the deterioration of
14 tensile strength [21], [22], and the exposure of wood to dilute acids in the pH range 2-3 induced
15 losses in toughness [24] However, the reports of these authors were from studies conducted in the
16 laboratory and they do not reflect the use of the material in areas with intense pollutants such as
17 those produced by volcanoes. Therefore, field assays to evaluate the impact of the volcanic acidic
18 environment on structural wood specimens would be valuable. To determine if the results on a
19 laboratory scale would be replicated or negligible in timber mechanical properties. Consequently,
20 Costa Rica is a tropical Central American country, located in a geo-volcanological active region,
21 where the Caribbean, Cocos, and Nazca tectonic plates converge In this country, the most
22 important active volcanic craters are protected in National Parks, [25], [26]. There the use of
23 structural wood could be an alternative for the creation of tourist facilities and infrastructure.
24 Consequently, this research introduces a novel approach by investigatin this construction material
25 degradation under uncontrolled conditions. Contributing with new understandings of how volcanic
26 acidity impacts mechanical properties of tropical species at early stages. The hypothesis proposes
27 that structural wood is suitable for the deployment of infrastructure in areas characterized by acidic
28 environments. Particularly near active volcanoes. Grounded in the assumption that wood is capable

1 to withstand the impact of acidity. Such resilience could potentially offer competitive advantages
2 over materials that suffer severe degradation and oxidation in tropical climates. These findings
3 could help to optimize the use of these materials and up-to-date technologies to improve efficiency,
4 productivity, and competitiveness in potential touristic applications. Hence, this research objective
5 is to evaluate the impact of the volcanic atmosphere on the mechanical properties (MOE and MOR)
6 of local species *Cupressus lusitanica* and *Tectona grandis* using structural size specimens in the
7 early stages of exposure (30 months).

8 **Materials and methods**

9 **Study sites, control of weather conditions, and acid variables**

10 For the study, two testing areas with similar altitudes and climatic conditions were selected. These
11 sites were: (a) Poás Volcano National Park (P) 10°10'10.36"N, 84°13'56.00"W, 35Km from San
12 José. It was chosen for its sustained volcanic activity and important touristic socio-economic
13 activity. (b) The witness site, Braulio Carrillo National Park (B.C.) 10°09'36"N 83°58'28W" was
14 chosen due to its similar altitude but without volcanic exposure. The study was carried out for 30
15 months from September 2020 to March 2023, with time series (3, 6, 9, 12, 18, 24, and 30 months).
16 The wood specimens were exposed in exhibitors separated from the ground, minimizing the impact
17 of biological degradation [27] (use class 3.2) [28]. Data on volcanic gas concentration were
18 obtained from the Costa Rican Volcanological and Seismological Observatory (OVSICORI). The
19 monitoring stations Expo-GAS, and Multi-GAS CO₂/SO₂ register data every 30 seconds. For this
20 study, only SO₂ was considered due to its predominant concentration concerning other gases. The
21 weather variables data were obtained from meteorological stations at the study sites (Davis
22 instruments, wireless-vantage-pro2) with UV radiation sensors, rain gauges (Will Lambrecht),
23 optical sensors, Weathering® Data Loggers (Campbell Scientific). Additionally, rainwater and fog
24 collectors were placed at the study sites (the latter arranged under an eave to collect only condensed
25 water from fog). Samples were analyzed monthly considering the pH level, the detection, and the
26 concentration of anions, chloride, fluoride, sulphate, and nitrate (Cl⁻, F⁻, NO₃⁻ and SO₄²⁻
27 respectively), analyzed by ion chromatography (HPLC, Dionex 5000, TCD, IonPac ® AS23).

28 **Materials**

29 The species, *Tectona grandis* L. (Teak) and *Cupressus lusitanica* Mill (Cypress) were chosen
30 considering their commercial relevance. Locally, Teak is the most exported-hardwood, highly

1 durable, according to EN 350-1:1994, due to the presence of extracts in its heartwood has strong
 2 decay resistance, and excellent dimensional stability, thus is often used for outdoors [29][30].
 3 While Cypress is the softwood with the most extensive local forestry plantations [31]. The study
 4 specimens were obtained from solid, sawn, and untreated wood. Teak was obtained in Rita de
 5 Guápiles (Limón) from 14-year-old forest plantations. Cypress was obtained from 40-year-old
 6 plantations located in San José de la Montaña (Heredia) both with structural dimensions (of) 2 x 4
 7 x 68” (48 x 98 x 1720 (mm)). Furthermore, the height-width ratio (d/b) was according to ASTM-
 8 D-198 [32]. The wood was oven-dried, to reach a moisture content of (12±2) %. Wood pieces
 9 were visually classified according to the local standard INTE C:100 [33] for the structural grade,
 10 and approximately 75% of the heartwood percentage was considered. The study specimens were
 11 arranged in experimental units, divided by both site and species, as shown in **Figure 1**. Wood
 12 samples were placed maintaining a distance of 0.25 m between them. They were supported without
 13 metal connectors to avoid moisture traps, placed at 0.60 m from the ground. Exhibitors were
 14 arranged southward to receive the highest amount of solar radiation. Tests were carried out on 256
 15 specimens (128 pieces of *Tectona grandis* and 128 pieces of *Cupressus lusitanica*, considering 32
 16 replicates for each study time/time series, 16 per specie, 8 per site)

27 **Figure 1.** Impact of the volcanic acidic atmosphere on the mechanical properties of Teak, hardwood (HW),
 28 and Cypress softwood (SW) in the early stages during 30 months of outdoor exposure. Two study sites,
 29 acid and control (P. and B.C), characterization of weather and acid variables. Mechanical properties (MOE,
 30 MOR), through time series, empirical models to describe the observed MOE tendency of each species.

1 **Static bending tests – obtaining MOE, MOR, LOP**

2 Samples were conditioned in a chamber (suitable for structural size samples) at 25°C and 60%
3 RH. Moisture content (MC) was determined according to ASTM D4933–16 [34] Standard Guide
4 for Moisture Conditioning of Wood and Wood-Based Materials. Due to periodic weightings
5 equilibrium is assumed to occur in 4-time constants. The static bending tests were carried out
6 loaded to the thirds, with two points of load, according to ASTM-D 198-15 [32]. Also named 4
7 points (support/load). The specimens were tested on a universal testing machine (MTS). The load
8 and average velocity to reach the maximum load in 4 min were considered. The placement of the
9 linear variation differential transformer (LVDT) was verified to measure the deformation and the
10 maximum load (F_{max}). MOE and MOR were determined according to [32]. The force in the limit
11 of proportionality (LOP), or the critical force required to generate a permanent deformation
12 (plastic, non-linear deformation) [35], [36], was calculated with Eq. 4 [37]

$$13 \quad LOP_{w4} = \frac{3F_E l_0}{4 \cdot b \cdot d^2} \quad (4)$$

14 Where LOP_{w4} is the proportionality limit (MPa), F_E is the force limit (N) determined from the
15 force-deformation diagram, with a 1% deviation from the linear equation, l_0 is the effective length
16 of the sample between the supports (mm), b is the width (mm), and d is the height (mm).

17 **Statistical analysis**

18 Variation of the mechanical properties of wood due to outdoor exposure is a complex multivariable
19 phenomenon. To reduce the level of uncertainty and error associated with the analysis process; a
20 careful control volume and study parameters delimitation was set up. A categorical analysis was
21 applied for the weather variable analysis establishing the intensity or concentration degree at which
22 the material was exposed per study site. Intensity and frequency levels were defined for each
23 variable, by considering the minimum value of the first quartile and the maximum value of the
24 third quartile of both site distributions, and the number of observations. The atmosphere was
25 characterized by wind speed, UV radiation, precipitation, relative humidity, and temperature.
26 Additionally, SO_2 , fog and rain pH, and SO_4^{2-} were measured to monitor the atmospheric acidity.
27 Profiles were created using Matlab®, and variable distribution was identified (t-2-sample test;
28 Wilcoxon test) using R Studio (v4.2.3; R Core Team 2023). The significant difference in the inter-
29 site variables was established with a significance level of 0.05, as shown in **Table 1**. Afterwards,
30 the analysis of the mechanical properties was obtained from the bending tests (time series points).

1 An average of 6 replicates (degrees of freedom) was employed at each point. As an approach facing
2 the material natural heterogeneity, homoscedasticity tests (Breusch-Pagan, R (v0.2.0), normality
3 of the residuals, and outliers' test detection (Dixon Outliers R (v0.15)) were performed. The effects
4 of weather variables by the site (intra-site) and between sites (inter-sites) were determined
5 considering the numerical values of the MOE and MOR with their confidence intervals (Bootstrap
6 method). Subsequently, a Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was performed, as an atmospheric
7 multivariate analysis. Its viability was established with the Bartlett test (differences of correlation
8 and identity matrices) and the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) adequacy factor. PCA allows us to
9 determine the variable's best distribution in each principal component (PC). Additionally, the
10 percentage of variance explained by each PC was calculated. Afterwards, to describe the sinusoidal
11 experimentally observed behaviour, a non-linear regression relating the MOE and the atmosphere's
12 PCs was applied.

13 **Model fitting on state variables**

14 Subsequently, a model on state variables was proposed. Allowing us to model dynamic systems in
15 the time domain. These can be represented by first-order differential Eq. (5)

$$\dot{x} = Ax + Bu \quad (5)$$

16 Where the variable \dot{x} denotes the derivative concerning the time of the state variable x . The vector
17 u is defined as a column vector of size $r \times 1$, where r encompasses all the input variables that can
18 affect the system. These input variables can also be expressed as a function of time. Furthermore,
19 matrices A and B represent the coefficients of the system. A is a square matrix of size $n \times n$, where
20 n corresponds to the number of state variables. B , on the other hand, is a matrix of size $r \times n$. In the
21 system, only one state variable represents the MOE. This variable is influenced by climatic
22 conditions, and the climate varies over time. To incorporate climatic variables the PC were used.
23 The model fitting for each species required a set of procedures using MATLAB® software.
24 Initially, the boundary conditions and the initial values of the parameters to be determined were
25 defined. Subsequently, with these conditions, the software solved the differential equation using
26 numerical methods, with the Ode45 function that applies the Runge-Kutta method. Once the MOE
27 result was obtained from the differential equation, it was compared with the experimental values
28 determined throughout 30 months of analysis using an objective function, Eq. (6).

$$Objective\ Function = \sum (MOE_{Experimental} - MOE_{Model})^2 \quad (6)$$

1 Afterwards, an optimization process to minimize the error was considered, using the previously
 2 defined objective function. For this purpose, the fminsearch function was used, which adjusts the
 3 model parameters iteratively until finding those that result in the lowest possible error.

4 Results and Discussion

5 A) Atmosphere characterization

6 In this study was imperative to demonstrate the acidic environment of the sites where the
 7 experiment was run. **Table 1** shows the climate variables with significant and non-significant inter-
 8 site differences ($\alpha_{0.05}$).

9 **Table 1. Climate variables analysis - inter-site differences**

10

Significant differences.			
Climate variable	Average B.C	Average Poás	p-value comparison
Rainwater – pH level	6.10	4.46	$9.356 \times 10^{-1}\zeta$
Rainwater -SO ₄ ²⁻ (mg/L)	0.19	3.96	$4.976 \times 10^{-4}\zeta$
Temperature (C °)	10.91	11.63	$7.9 \times 10^{-4}\zeta$
Radiation (W/m ²)	279.04	239.77	$3.114 \times 10^{-2}\zeta$
Wind speed (km/h)	4.37	2.90	$5.908 \times 10^{-4}\dagger$
No significant differences.			
Precipitation (mm/día)	14.08	14.94	$6.612 \times 10^{-1}\dagger$
Relative humidity (%)	92.52	94.06	$1.31 \times 10^{-1}\dagger$

ζ Wilcoxon sum test (non-normal distribution), \dagger t-test- 2 samples (normal distribution), significance level 0.05

11 As is explained in the introduction, SO₂ reacts in atmospheric conditions producing sulphate ions
 12 and ions hydronium. This acid condition was analyzed in two ways, 1) determining the rain acidity
 13 and 2) determining the fog acidity. The fog-pH average was 3.34 ± 0.52 . This is in the range
 14 reported by [23], this pH lower than 3.5 could affect mechanical performance according to their
 15 report. In this research, at the site (P) the rainwater pH was identified as 4.46. Hence, 33% of the
 16 observations correspond to a rainwater pH level between 3 and 4. However, if a pH level of less
 17 than 5 is considered, 73% of the time the acid condition would prevail. While in (B.C.)
 18 concentrations in those ranges were not identified. Since the frequency in B.C. was concentrated
 19 in pH 6 and 7, it can be considered that the site is close to hydrogen potential neutrality. This
 20 concentration shows a clear environmental difference between both study sites (**Figure 2**)

1 **Figure 2.** Atmospheric Characterization Data- experimental acidic profiles a) pH acidity level detected in
2 both sites' rainwater (R (rain) F (fog)), b) pH -P frequency. c) Frequency pH- B.C. Low pH level: < 3.7,
3 intermediate: 3.7 – 6.7 and high: > 6.7.

4 In the fog, the microdroplets (10-20 (μm)), maintain the acid environment even when there is no
5 precipitation [38]. This condition could affect the material since the erosion rate could increase
6 [23]. As expected, in the P site the analysis of the fog's condensed water showed more anions than
7 those detected in rain Fog-SO₄²⁻ was (23.44 ± 22.99) mg/L Rainwater-SO₄²⁻ (3.96 ± 0.75 mg/L).
8 No evidence of variation in the dry or rainy season was found. Additionally, the atmospheric
9 concentration of SO₂ measured with monitoring stations at the volcanic site, presented mainly low
10 concentration values, in the range of (0-1.5) ppm (**Figure 3**).

17 **Figure 3.** Acidic Agent Concentration in P Site a) SO₂. Low level: < 0.086 ppm, intermediate: 0.086 – 0.23
18 mg/L and high: > 0.23 ppm; Average-high levels: (low-high: < 1.1 ppm, intermediate-high: 1.1 – 2.6 ppm
19 and high-high: > 2.6 ppm. b) SO₄²⁻ low level < 2 mg/L, intermediate: 2 – 6 mg/L and high: > 6 mg.
20

21 Moreover, the observed peaks correspond to eruptive processes in which gases have higher
22 intensity. Although occurring for short periods, they could affect the analysed system if their
23 frequency were constant, the obtained average value was (0.86 ± 1.06) ppm, it might be considered
24 a low average, but its dissolution and constancy could impact the material degradation process.
25 Nevertheless, in this experimental study, it should be considered that the precipitation in the study
26 sites is considerably higher than in other world latitudes. Around 14 mm/day on average (between
27 50-100) mm/day (rainy season), with maximum values of 200 mm/day (as shown in **Figure 7**),
28 and the microscopic effect of acidity (pH, SO₂, SO₄²⁻) could be limited by diffusion phenomena
29 only in the surface layers/areas. For this purpose, it is recommended to carry out additional studies
30 on the porosity, tortuosity, and sorption behaviour of the species to have a better understanding of
31 this microscale effect. Meanwhile, the experimental results in structural specimens indicated a

1 significant difference ($\alpha 0.05$) in the acid condition between the field sites. In the next section (the
 2 effect of the acidic atmosphere on the mechanical properties) it will be explained that no statistical
 3 difference in the wood species MOE inter-sites was found. It seems that constantly high levels of
 4 precipitation may quickly remove acids (wash them away). But further investigation shall be done
 5 to confirm this theory. The main result for early-stage outdoor exposure is that the MOE has not
 6 been affected at a significant level. On the other hand, the synergistic effect of temperature should
 7 also be considered [21]. As observed in **Figure 4**, at the control site B.C. the temperature was
 8 slightly lower than in P (between 0.5 and 1°C). Whereas the temperature variation inter-sites were
 9 similar. The average temperature was approximately 10°C, relatively low values for the tropical
 10 climate at this latitude, (which usually ranges between (18-30) °C). Therefore, the low temperature
 11 in the study sites could reduce the activation of the reactions by acids, and the degradation of the
 12 fibres caused by natural agents (fungi).

19 **Figure 4.** Atmospheric characterization data- Temperature Profiles a)variation at both places (P, B.C), b)
 20 Frequency in P. and b) Frequency in B.C. Low level:<10.5°C, intermediate: 10.5–12 °C and high: > 12 °C.
 21

22 As shown in **Figure 5**. UV radiation (approximately 240-280 W/m²) was significantly different
 23 between the study sites and has a low average magnitude. Considering that in Costa Rica the
 24 material could be exposed to up to 1000 W/m² [39]. Hence, in this tropical country, the radiation
 25 and temperature of the two study sites are variables of similar magnitude for the assessment of
 26 material degradation and engineering applications.

1 **Figure 5.** Atmospheric characterization data- Radiation profile a) Intensity and frequency of solar
 2 irradiation. Profile at both sites (P and B.C), b) Frequency in Poás, c) Frequency in B.C. The levels for solar
 3 irradiation: low level: < 210 W/m², intermediate: 210 – 300 W/m² and high: > 300 W/m².
 4

5 According to the Costa Rican National Meteorological Institute, in this region, wind speed and
 6 direction depend on "El Niño/Southern Oscillation" (ENSO) phenomenon, and it varies each year
 7 in the Latin America Region. Generally, between August and November, the intertropical
 8 convergence zone is located in this country. It generates a greater force of equatorial winds that
 9 affects the direction of the wind and the increase in rainfall [40][41]. In this regard, consideration
 10 should be given to wind speed being an important climatic element for the global mass transfer
 11 coefficient. It directly affects the diffusion of unbound water in the wood. Differences in maximum
 12 wind speed were also observed in the study sites (**Figure 6**).

19 **Figure 6.** Atmospheric characterization data- Wind Profile a) Comparison of inter-site wind speed (P) and
 20 (B.C). b) Frequency in P. c) Frequency in B.C. Low level: < 2 km/h, intermediate level: 2 – 5.5 km/h, and
 21 high level: > 5.5 km/h

22 On the other hand, the average monthly precipitation for both sites was 14.52 mm/day and 380.30
 23 mm/month. B.C: 383.57 mm/month and P: 376.92 mm/ month, (**Figure 7**).

1 **Figure 7.** Atmospheric characterization data- Precipitation Profile a) Inter-site precipitation levels (P and
 2 B.C), b) Frequency in P. c) Frequency in B.C. Low level: < 9.8 mm/day, medium level: 9.8 mm/day < x <
 3 20.3 mm/day, and high level > 20.3 mm/day

4
 5 Local precipitation levels are among the highest levels worldwide expected, half of the world area
 6 has less than 1 mm/day [42]–[44]. Furthermore, relative humidity (RH) also makes a substantial
 7 difference in comparison with other world latitudes [45] and thus in the wood performance. The
 8 overall average RH at both sites was close to 93%. **Figure 8** shows that the predominant levels
 9 were 90-95%. Although variations of approximately 7% were recorded on the same day. Humidity
 10 changes occur for a short period; hence, the material does not stabilize and quickly returns to high
 11 humidity. Although the RH levels of the tropical zones are estimated between 80%-90% [32][37].
 12 The experimental values obtained in study zones were higher. Regarding this, an aspect to clarify
 13 is that the sensors provide reliable values up to a value of 95% humidity, but higher values to a
 14 maximum saturation of 100% RH at these locations are also common based on psychometrics.
 15 This detail does not affect the analysis nor the conclusions but rather shows the resistance of these
 16 two wood species under the utmost conditions during the study period.

25 **B) Evaluation of the effect of the acidic atmosphere on the mechanical properties**

26 **B.1 Modulus of elasticity of *Cupressus lusitanica***

27 The average magnitude of the Modulus of elasticity of cypress (Cypress-MOE) between Poás and
 28 B.C. was similar (8.52 ± 2.37) GPa and (8.50 ± 2.71) GPa, respectively, considering the results of
 29 the time series. **Figure 9** shows the experimental profile curves for the species and their
 30 corresponding confidence interval. As an important result, no significant difference in the MOE
 31 between sites was determined as a result of the statistical tests ($\alpha = 0.05$). Moreover, it is interesting
 32 to observe a similar curve trend in both species, despite their differences due to being softwood or

1 hardwood. Note the oscillatory sinusoidal behaviour over time. It seems that the environment
 2 regularly influences this mechanical property, depending on the season, rainy or dry, and not
 3 relative humidity. The observed MOE slight reduction matches with the rainy season, which agrees
 4 with a higher unbound water present and a reduced capacity for water diffusion; even though the
 5 pieces were experimentally conditioned for the mechanical analysis.

13 **Figure 9.** MOE trends at both sites, both species in 30 months of exposure outdoors.
 14 Study times in months t0 = September 2020, t3 = December 2021, t6 = March 2022, t9 = June. 2022, t12=
 15 September. 2022, t18= March 2022, t24= September. 2022, t30= March 2023.
 16

17 Regarding the observed oscillatory behaviour of Cypress-MOE over time, **Table 2** summarizes the
 18 obtained results. The control specimen’s Cypress-MOE average was (8.92 ± 2.02) GPa. At 3
 19 months a minor reduction was obtained. The decreasing process continued, obtaining a minimum
 20 value in month 6 (6.38 ± 3.76) GPa. In contrast, per months 9 and 12, there was an increase that
 21 continued until month 18, where the maximum values were obtained (10.55 ± 3.46) GPa.
 22 Subsequently, at 24-30 months, a slight reduction was observed, which seems to show a new cycle.

23 **Table 2. Comparison inter-sites Cypress-MOE**

Study time (months)	MOE Average P. site (GPa)	MOE Average B.C site (GPa)
3	9.30 ± 3.64	8.90 ± 2.82
6	6.70 ± 3.48	6.07 ± 3.89
9	7.58 ± 2.06	8.44 ± 4.29
12	8.93 ± 3.37	9.09 ± 4.13
18	10.44 ± 3.22	10.66 ± 3.57
24	8.25 ± 2.36	7.91 ± 2.85
30	8.44 ± 2.53	8.40 ± 2.61

24

1 On the other hand, considering that an atmospheric description is a multivariate system, it could
 2 be a complex approach to use it directly in a model. Fortunately, in weather data sets one variable
 3 might be measuring the same driving principle governing the behavior of the atmospheric system.
 4 This study had an extensive data acquisition system applied in each site to visualize redundant
 5 information. **Table 3** shows the PCs determined after an atmospheric variable correlation study,
 6 and the variance explained by each PC I shown in **Figure 10**. This rigorous quantitative method
 7 allows the simplification of the climatic data to express summarized variables and propose an
 8 empirical model. In this line, the variance obtained using two PCs was estimated as 0.73, and the
 9 relative difference using three PCs was just an increase of 0.1 approximately.

Table 3. Principal Components 10

	PC1	PC2	
Temperature (mean)	-0.49	-0.05	11
Precipitation (mean)	-0.40	-0.10	12
Wind speed	0.42	-0.14	
HR (mean)	-0.37	0.17	13
Radiation	0.52	-0.03	
SO42-	0.04	0.69	14
pH	-0.08	-0.68	

Figure 10 Percentage of Variance explained by each PC.

15
 16 Furthermore, it was observed that for an increase in PC1, the wind and radiation had a significant
 17 rise, and the sulphate contribution was negligible. The temperature, precipitation, and relative
 18 humidity (RH) had an inverse behaviour. When PC2 increased a significant influence of SO_4^{2-} was
 19 obtained and in a lower magnitude, the relative humidity participated. The pH decreasing agrees
 20 with the sulphate ions magnitude, considering an anion higher concentration, the lower pH is
 21 obtained, thus, as a consistent result from the PCA. Then, the PCs proposed have physically
 22 consistent relationships and contributions. Subsequently, to integrate the principal components as
 23 input variables, it is crucial to have information regarding their temporal variation. Therefore,
 24 modelling the behaviour of these components throughout the 30 months of the experiment was
 25 carried out; for this, a non-linear regression using MATLAB software with the `nlinfit` function was
 26 carried out. Regarding 1 PC1, the following model has been identified, which exhibits a
 27 coefficient of determination of 0.78 and a mean square error (MSE) of 0.72. Eq. (7)

$$CP1(t) = 2.07 \text{ sen}(0.552t + 2.50) - 0.047 \quad (7)$$

1 The observed behaviour is consistent with expectations since PC1 is mainly composed of variables
 2 that follow annual cycles, such as temperature, precipitation, and radiation, among others. This
 3 statement is supported by determining the period of the wave evidenced in **Figure 11**, estimated
 4 at 11.4 months. It should be noted that, in both sites, these variables show very similar behaviour,
 5 which allows working with a model that predicts the behaviour in both sites.

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12 **Figure 11.** The behavior of Principal Component 1 concerning time.

13 On the other hand, PC2 is made up of variables that explain the acidity of the atmosphere, such as
 14 the concentration of SO_4^{2-} and pH. On the other hand, it was already determined that the acidity
 15 between the study sites is different. Therefore, to account for this difference, independent
 16 modelling was carried out for each site. These models were integrated as independent inputs into
 17 the state variable model, each with specific coefficients to reflect the particularities of each site.
 18 Concerning the variation of PC2 at the Poás site, the model presented in Eq. 8 was formulated.
 19 This model has a coefficient of determination of 0.92 and an MSE of 0.63. The adjustment results
 20 are shown in **Figure 12**.

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$$PC2_p(t) = 2.64 \text{ sen}(0.22t - 5.66) - 1.11 \quad (8)$$

1 **Figure 12.** The behaviour of PC 2 in Poás concerning time.

2 On the other hand, the behaviour of PC2 at the B.C control site is described by Eq. 9, with a
 3 coefficient of determination of 0.94 and an MSE of 0.032. It is important to highlight that the main
 4 difference concerning PC2 in P lies in the magnitude of the value of PC2. These values are
 5 expected to be low, and this expectation is confirmed by looking at both the amplitude in Eq. 8
 6 and **Figure 13.**

$$7 \quad CP2_B(t) = 0.728 \text{ sen}(0.27t - 3.67) - 0.61 \quad (9)$$

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15 **Figure 13.** The behavior of Principal Component 2 in B.C concerning time.

16 Once all the inputs to the system were fitted as a function of time, the first-order differential
 17 equation describing the variation of the MOE concerning time was defined. It is important to note
 18 that matrix A was reduced to a scalar since there is only one state variable Eq. (10).

$$\frac{dMOE}{dt} = A MOE + [B_1 \ B_2 \ B_3] \begin{bmatrix} 2.07 \text{ sen}(0.552t + 2.50) - 0.047 \\ 2.64 \text{ sen}(0.22t - 5.66) - 1.11 \\ 0.728 \text{ sen}(0.27t - 3.67) - 0.61 \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

19 The coefficients in the differential equation are specific to each wood species and are characterized
 20 by particular MOE values. This allows us to describe the system with a coefficient of determination
 21 of 0.83 and an MSE of 0.29. On the other hand, in the case of cypress, the following expression
 22 was obtained, which has a coefficient of determination of 0.86 and an MSE of 0.23. Eq. (11)

$$\frac{dMOE}{dt} = -0.10 MOE + [-0.03 - 0.60 - 2.28] \begin{bmatrix} 2.07 \text{ sen}(0.552t + 2.50) - 0.047 \\ 2.64 \text{ sen}(0.22t - 5.66) - 1.11 \\ 0.728 \text{ sen}(0.27t - 3.67) - 0.61 \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

1 To validate the developed model, two validation points were selected, as shown in **Figure 14**. In
 2 this figure, it is observed that the validation experimental points are close to the values predicted
 3 by the model for Cypress-MOE.

12 **Figure 14.** Graphics of Cypress-MOE model and model on state variables validation.

14 **B.2 Modulus of elasticity of *Tectona grandis***

15 The modulus of elasticity for Teak (Teak-MOE) on average was (14.20 ± 4.17) GPa and $(13.82 \pm$
 16 $3.81)$ GPa for Poás and B.C, respectively, which are characteristic values for hardwood species.
 17 The confidence intervals are depicted in **Figure 9**, previously discussed, and **Table 4** shows the
 18 inter-site comparison of the Teak-MOE. Note that there is no statistical evidence ($\alpha_{0.05}$) of a
 19 significant variation between sites, but the same sinusoidal tendency can be seen.

20 **Table 4. Inter-sites Teak-MOE Comparison**

21 Study time (months)	MOE Average P (GPa)	MOE Average B.C(GPa)
22 3	15.52 ± 6.66	11.94 ± 7.57
23 6	13.43 ± 6.96	12.78 ± 5.56
24 9	13.65 ± 1.82	13.78 ± 1.83
12	14.29 ± 2.43	14.92 ± 1.98
18	16.22 ± 4.63	16.38 ± 3.24
24	12.65 ± 4.75	13.40 ± 3.88
30	13.67 ± 1.91	13.53 ± 2.59

1 In synthesis, the Teak-MOE for the controls was (13.84 ± 3.13) GPa. For months 3 and 6 the
 2 obtained value at both sites decreased. Subsequently, for months 9 and 12 it increased, reaching
 3 maximum values in month 18 (16.30 ± 4.01) GPa. In 24 and 30 months it increased at both sites.
 4 The coefficients in the differential equation for Teak are shown in Eq. (12).

$$\frac{dMOE}{dt} = -0.52 MOE + [-0.10 - 0.39 - 1.72] \begin{bmatrix} 2.07 \text{sen}(0.552t + 2.50) - 0.047 \\ 2.64 \text{sen}(0.22t - 5.66) - 1.11 \\ 0.728 \text{sen}(0.27t - 3.67) - 0.61 \end{bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

5 This allows us to describe the system with a coefficient of determination of 0.83 and an MSE of
 6 0.29. (Figure 15).

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15 **Figure 15.** Graphics of Teak-MOE model and model on state variables validation.
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17 Thus, a model was experimentally obtained that adequately describes the oscillatory behaviour of
 18 the MOE in each of the species/sites where the field tests were carried out for 30 months. Although
 19 the variation of the MOE was not substantial, it means that its mechanical performance is not
 20 affected by the degradation attributed to volcanic acidity. The model allows an explanation of the
 21 variations observed over the study time. This can also be observed in the validation. This model is
 22 novel since proposes an approach to include the data of the atmospheric variables of tropical
 23 countries and volcanic activity as input data. Allowing to estimate a potential variation of MOE
 24 for the studied species, under the conditions affected according to the rainy or dry seasons.

25 **B.3 Modulus of rupture of both species**

1 The experimental modulus of rupture at the end of the study were Teak-MOR (68.49 ± 8.34) MPa
 2 and Cypress-MOR (39.58 ± 6.60) MPa, on average. **Figure 16** shows a MOR variation for both
 3 species following the same tendency during the study period. Note at the beginning a depression
 4 that slightly recovers with a pronounced slope up to a similar average to month 0, when the study
 5 started. In contrast with the MOE experimental results, the MOR values showed a considerable
 6 standard deviation making it difficult to conclude about a specific phenomenon related to the
 7 material changes or the affectation due to the fibres modification with macroscopic impact. Despite
 8 that, the MOR reflects in general terms, the way that the energy is managed inside the material
 9 (elastic and plastic deformation) up to rupture.

17 **Figure 16.** MOR trends at both sites, both species in 30 months of exposure outdoors
 18 Study times in months t0 = September. 2020, t3 = December 2021, t6 = March 2022, t9 = June. 2022,
 19 t12= September. 2022, t18= March 2022, t24= September. 2022, t30= March 2023. The control MOR was
 20 Cypress- MOR (41.31 ± 9.20) and Teak- MOR (74.738 ± 12.47).
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22 MOR average experimental results suggest a sinusoidal tendency, but longer study periods should
 23 be run to verify this theory. The scope of this study is for the early degradation stage up to 30
 24 months. Comparing the MOR and MOE general trend, it is interesting to observe that the
 25 oscillation (up and down) presented in the MOE in the MOR seems to occur slower. For the study
 26 period, it can be mentioned that the MOR is not considerably affected as a mechanical property.

27 **B.4 Limit of proportionality**

28 **Figure 17** shows the experimental values of the proportionality limit during the 30 months of
 29 study. For the hardwood, it was obtained a range between (20-30) GPa (Teak-LOP). These results
 30 agree with reported values for other hardwood species, such as Babiak et al., [46] for oak (*Quercus*

1 *robur* L.). In the case of Cypress-LOP, the result was near 10 GPa, with less variation than the
 2 hardwood, which is consistent with values reported by the same author for fir (*Picea abies* L.), at
 3 slightly higher moisture contents (CH 14-16%) and for softwood. It seems that the stiffness could
 4 barely vary, and the force applied in the viscoplastic area as a measure of the wood's deformation
 5 resistance remains in the same range, as stated by Schellberg, D. [47].

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16 **Figure 17.** LOP trends at both sites, both species in 30 months of exposure outdoors
 17 Study times in months t0 = September. 2020, t3 = December 2021, t6 = March 2022, t9 = June. 2022,
 18 t12= September. 2022, t18= March 2022, t24= September. 2022, t30= March 2023

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20 Complementary, the failure mode tendency over time was analysed according to ASTM D-143,
 21 D198 [32], [48]. It was determined a similar failure mode distribution for each species, and no
 22 evident modification over time was found suggesting additional information to consider. Finally,
 23 based on these results it can be deduced that the wood material for early stages of exposure (30
 24 months) of structural size specimens did not have significant affectation by acidic environment.
 25 The main mechanical properties such as MOE, MOR, force-deformation curves, LOP estimation,
 26 and failure mode, give a theoretical and practical framework to estimate the material performance
 27 of touristic natural facilities. Then, the impact of the volcanic atmosphere on the mechanical
 28 properties of *Cupressus lusitanica* and *Tectona grandis* shall not interfere with architecture
 29 applications using this wood material to design and build small infrastructures. Of course, it is
 30 recommended to consider the interactions of climate variables for extended periods (long-term
 31 studies).

32

1 **Conclusions**

2 In conclusion, this research has undertaken a comprehensive evaluation of the impact of volcanic
3 atmospheric conditions on the mechanical properties (MOE and MOR) of *Cupressus lusitanica*
4 and *Tectona grandis* structural-size specimens over a 30-month exposure period. Key findings and
5 conclusions drawn from this study are as follows:

6 **Similar Mechanical Properties Environments:** Despite the acidic concentration in the volcanic
7 field study, the present investigation determined that there are no significant differences (α 0.05)
8 in the mechanical properties of *Tectona grandis* and *Cupressus lusitanica* structural-size specimens
9 in early-stage outdoor exposure in tropical sites. This suggests that these materials can be
10 considered viable for use in wooden architecture (infrastructure) within such hostile environments.

11 **Unique Atmospheric Conditions:** In volcanic areas, the study identified that the water condensed
12 from the fog can reach highly acidic pH values and a substantial concentration of fog SO_4^{2-} ions,
13 significantly higher than those observed in other tropical climates. While atmospheric SO_2 had low
14 concentration levels throughout the experiment, the primary contributor to acidic conditions was
15 intense precipitation resulting in acid fog conditions.

16 **Mechanical Property Trends:** Both sites and species exhibited an oscillatory trend in MOE over
17 the study period. The effect of outdoor exposure was found to be similar for both volcanic and
18 non-volcanic sites.

19 **Principal Component Analysis (PCA):** A PCA method was successfully employed to describe
20 the complex atmospheric system, explaining 70% of the total variation considering PC1 and PC2.

21 **Climate-Based Model:** The research successfully established a climate-based model to estimate
22 the MOE of *Tectona grandis* and *Cupressus lusitanica* during the early stages of degradation in
23 structural-sized specimens. Statistical parameters and experimental validation demonstrated an
24 accurate approach to monitor MOE variation, particularly for softwood and hardwood forecast
25 variations. However, it was observed that for structural-sized samples, there was no significant
26 elastic variation in the early stages.

27 **Mechanical Property Changes:** Over the study period, Cypress-MOE decreased by 5.6%, and
28 Teak-MOE decreased by 1.59% compared to the initial measurements. Although these results may
29 be considered insignificant for structural applications, they are consistent with anticipated

1 variations in softwood and hardwood. Additionally, Cypress-MOR increased by 7.38%, and Teak-
2 MOR increased by 5%, potentially indicating changes in fibre composition due to outdoor
3 exposure.

4 In summary, this research provides valuable insights into the behaviour of structural-sized wood
5 specimens exposed to volcanic atmospheric conditions. It underscores the suitability of *Tectona*
6 *grandis* and *Cupressus lusitanica* for use in timber architecture within such environments, while
7 also shedding light on the unique atmospheric factors influencing their mechanical properties.
8 Furthermore, the development of a climate-based model offers a promising approach for
9 monitoring these properties during the early stages of degradation, with potential implications for
10 material selection and design considerations in volcanic regions.

11 12 **Recommendations**

13 The outdoor exposure effect on wood mechanical properties has been limited to early stages, 30 months,
14 and a longer-term study is required to assess the longer-term impact. On the other hand, the model
15 developed shall be used only for the studied species and tropical climates. Considering the effect of acidity
16 (pH, SO₂ and SO₄²⁻) could be governed by the diffusion process, it is recommended to carry out studies on
17 the porosity, tortuosity, and sorption behaviour of the species.

18 19 **CRedit authorship contribution statement**

20 Viviana Paniagua: Writing, review & editing, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Jimena
21 Montero, investigation-analysis, review & editing. Cindy Torres: Conceptualization, Writing an original
22 draft, review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Beatriz González Rodrigo: Writing, review
23 & editing.

24
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26
27 **Data availability:** Data will be made available on request.

28
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39
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1 Abbreviations

2	ASTM	American Society for Testing and Materials.
3	B.C.	Braulio Carrillo, (control site. Non-Acid site)
4	CI	Confidence intervals
5	CICIMA	Center for Research in Materials Science and Engineering, University of Costa Rica
6	Cl ⁻	Chloride. Anion analyzed in rainwater
7	CNE	National Emergency Commission.
8	F ⁻	Fluoride. Anion analyzed in rainwater
9	FUNDECOR	Central Volcanic Mountain Range Development Foundation (meteorological station)
10	H ₂ O ₂	Hydrogen peroxide.
11	H ₂ S	Hydrogen sulphide.
12	H ₂ SO ₄	Sulphuric acid.
13	HCl	Hydrogen chloride.
14	HSO ₃ ⁻	Bisulphide
15	IMN	National Meteorological Institute.
16	INTE	INTECO Institute of Technical Standards of Costa Rica
17	KMO	Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin, adequacy factor, to perform APC-PCA.
18	LANAMME	National Laboratory of Materials and Structural Models
19	LAQAT-UNA	Atmosphere Chemistry Laboratory-UNA National University
20	LOP	Limit of proportionality.
21	LVDT	Linear Variation Differential Transformer
22	MC	Moisture content.
23	MOE	Modulus of elasticity.
24	MOR	Modulus of rupture
25	MSE	Mean squared error, mean square error.
26	MTS	A universal testing machine, an acronym in English.
27	NO ₃ ⁻	Nitrate. Anion analyzed in rainwater
28	OVSICORI	Volcanological and Seismological Observatory of Costa Rica
29	P.	Poás, name of the Volcano and National Park (acid site).
30	PC	Principal Component
31	PCA	Principal Component Analysis, CPA
32	RH	Relative humidity
33	SINAC	National Conservation Areas System of Costa Rica.
34	SO ₂	Sulphur dioxide.
35	SO ₄ ²⁻	Sulphate. Anion analyzed in collected rainwater

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